

Navigating the Blue: An Overview of the Exemplary Scholarship in Blue Humanities

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***Abstract:** Water is not just a resource for living but a dynamic force shaping human identity, history and environment. It cannot be treated as a vestige when the colonialism of the terrestrial assets comes to an end with all the deep pockets empty. In fact, rivers are considered as the cradles of civilizations, on the planet, with which mankind is deeply associated for their fostering and advancements towards the modern societies. Water bodies, whether they are the seas, oceans, rivers, lakes, glaciers etc., cannot be isolated or neglected in understanding the ecosystems, and moreover a deep awareness is needed to recognize their vital role in maintaining the socio-ecological balance. A part from the scientific study of these water bodies, a lot of research is being done in the aspect of literature, in the name of 'Blue Humanities', which may surface the histories of cultures and the lives of the indigenous peoples that are inherently linked to the oceans and the other waters. A profound exploration of these aspects can help in addressing the raising concerns of environmental issues such as pollution and climate change, which are questioning the human beings' chances of survival on the planet. In this context, this paper attempts to explore some of the literary writings which are*

really concerned with the framework of Blue Humanities and are striving to change the hegemonic approach of land to water, thus making the aquatic bodies as the center of not only of human imagination, but also for human survival.

Keywords: Blue humanities, water bodies, socio-ecological balance, eco-systems, environmental crises, sublimity

Overview:

As the exploration of planet has reached its culmination in this age of modern science and technology, man has left nothing his behind but only the devastation on one hand and the socio-environmental crisis on the other. This situation of despondency created the necessity to scour at the alternatives for the betterment of the planet by looking towards the oceans and seas which are considered as the places for the origins of human cultures, with a paradigm shift from land-centered perceptions to the water-centered perceptions in order to examine, how the oceans and seas have shaped the culture of the mankind. This approach paved the way for various writings on the aquatic life especially by creating specialized disciplines in the worldwide academia, thus placing every study under the umbrella term, ‘Blue Humanities’, coined by an English professor, Steve Menz, in his book *An Introduction to Blue Humanities*(2024). Historicization of the oceans is one of the striking trends exploring ocean histories that go beyond white man’s colonial cultures, and hence the Maritime science once concerned about water’s surface is now concerned with life in the ocean itself. This cultural turn which was started in eighteenth and nineteenth centuries has given rise to numerous studies in the blue humanities as it provides a frame work to study the oceans and other water bodies, with an emphasis on the relationship between the life of underwater and the human experience, thus bringing

together various disciplines such as Literature, History, Philosophy, Cultural Studies etc. Being a transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary area of study, Blue Humanities gave rise to the ecological thinking, when mariners discovered the damage that invasive species of plants and animals could do on small islands around the world. This heightened ecological awareness has prompted a significant shifting focus, about the oceans, from the study of shipwrecks, voyages, and sailors' expeditions to a deeper exploration of the life of water bodies, the experiences in indigenous land communities, their intrinsic relationship with the oceans, and the richness of marine ecosystems. Such an approach offers a more comprehensive understanding of contemporary ecological crises and underscores the urgent need to preserve ecological balance, with the framework of Blue Humanities, which was characterized by disciplinary fluidity, maritime history, nautical literatures, marine sciences, sea narratives etc. This framework involves a disciplinary approach that uses cultural, literary, and historical lenses to understand humanity's relationship with water, particularly oceans and seas, highlighting the humanity's mutual dependence on the ocean and giving a call for action to protect and preserve, these water resources in the wake of climate change and rising sea levels.

Advertently, Blue Humanities, questions traditional, land-locked ways of thinking and perception, thus aiming to redress the imbalance in the academic scholarship, that has traditionally focused on terrestrial subjects. As a discipline it should counter a westernized colonial depiction of land in the narratives which always makes land to precede the water. In such counter studies, *Odyssey*, a classical work by Homer, and one of the foundational texts of world literature focus on examining the epic's depiction of the ocean and its relationship with humanity, with a water-centric

perception, considering the cultural, ecological and existential significance of the Mediterranean Sea. The sea has always been depicted as a dynamic force with its wrath and perils inherent, symbolizing the spirit of freedom and adventure. Hence, instead of considering the sea as a backdrop of Odysseus' story, the Blue Humanities frame work, reconsiders it as a source of powerful transformative entity, with a combination of life sustaining resources, immense dangers, profound mysteries etc., all together, testing the human resilience. The epic's extensive voyages across the sea are interpreted as a fundamental human impulse to explore, discover and confront the unknown. In this perspective Odysseus's journey can be examined through the human consciousness, encountering the wilderness and vastness of the watery world, highlighting the ocean's symbolic and spiritual importance in their culture. Apart from the dangerous voyages and different incidents that happened in the epic, simultaneous themes can be framed through a contemporary understanding of the ocean as a complex, dynamic, and vital element of human experience and the planet. The sea is not only a dangerous, chaotic force, but also a place of profound personal growth and transformation, and with the lenses of ecocritical perspective of Blue Humanities, the poem can be analyzed as a precursor to modern ecological thought, exploring the ocean's fragility and the long-standing relationship between human actions and marine ecosystems.

Sea of Cortez, (1941), is another wonderful water narrative by Steinbeck and Edward F. Ricketts, which gives an account of a marine biological expedition of the Gulf of California, popularly known as the Sea of Cortez. Ricketts, collaborating with his friend Steinbeck, went on this expedition to explore and document the diversity of the marine life, under the waters, aiming to capture, preserve and catalog numerous species. The work offers

philosophical insights, drawing parallels between human and marine life, contributing to both scientific literature and nature writing and highlighting the intricate relationships within marine ecosystems. During their six-week expedition, Ricketts and Steinbeck, captured thousands of specimens and nearly 560 species of marine invertebrates, which was the first ever collection of such kind of fauna in the Gulf of California. As invertebrates are known for their high sensitivity to changes in water quality, nutrient levels, pollutants, naturally, their existence and their diversity indicate the purity of the water bodies, acting as the bio-indicators. Also, they are the food sources for other aquatic bodies and create habitats such as the coral reefs, thus playing a key role in sustaining the ecosystem. Hence, the collection of such specimens, and their record in the book, needless to say, has given a first public call for the conservation in the Gulf of California, and created an alarming awareness about the region among the both scientists and even the public. Since its publication, the chronicle has inspired hundreds and thousands of young students to devote their careers to marine and field biology and created a profound impact on the American environmental consciousness.

Rachel Carson, an American biologist, writer and conservationist, was known for her advocacy in advancing marine conservation and the global environmental movement with her ground breaking works, *Sea trilogy* (1941-1955) and *Silent Spring* (1962). Specifically, *Sea Around Us*, one in the trilogy, demonstrates the deep connection between the sea and all life on earth, including the regulation of climate and the support of diverse ecosystems. It is considered as a classic nature writing that details the history, science and ecology of earth's oceans, blending scientific accuracy with poetic prose. The text explores the deep sea, its varied life forms, and the powerful influence of tides and

currents, promoting the awareness of the ocean's vital role in the global eco system, which still resonates today. Carson's work both anticipates and complicates Blue Humanities concerns by decentering the man's approach to the sea, narrating deep time, and foregrounding the oceanic agency, yet still reflecting Cold war, Anthropocentric views, and even gendered contexts. It invites the readers to see the ocean not as a backdrop but as a dynamic living force, which has increasingly altered by human activity, impacting the marine eco systems. As a counter approach to the sea, from the land centric view, Carson, highlights the origin and the role of marine life in sustaining the planet. She draws the equal significance to the seasons both on the land and in the seas with the depiction of the spring season and the key changes that happens in the waters, during the period, in the following lines,

“In the sea as on the land, spring is a time for the renewal of life. During the long months of winter in the temperate zones the surface waters have been absorbing the cold. Now the heavy water begins to sink, slipping down and displacing the warmer layers below. Rich stores of minerals have been accumulating on the floor of the continental shelf—some freighted down the rivers from the lands; some derived from sea creatures that have died and whose remains have drifted down to the bottom; some from the shells ...Nothing is wasted in the sea; every particle of material is used over and over again, first by one creature, then by another. And when in spring the waters are deeply stirred, the warm bottom water brings the surface a rich supply of minerals, ready for use by the new forms of life”
(Carson 29)

As Blue Humanities encourage a deeper reading of the water narratives, highlighting the themes of migration, ecology, resilience etc., the field places oceans, seas and waterways at the center of cultural, historical and environmental discussions. *The Social Construction of the Ocean*, by Philip Steinberg, is one such ground breaking work, which makes its central argument that the ocean is not simply a natural space or an empty void waiting to be used, but it is a socially constructed space whose boundaries, meanings and uses are shaped by history, culture, politics and economics. Steinberg insists that the ocean has always been made by human societies, constructed as a space of fear, freedom, circulation, or territory depending on cultural and political needs and this reminds us how we think about the sea, shapes how we use and govern it. With his profound understanding and observation of the sea and its fluidity, Steinberg asserts that, humans continually impose structures on it in the name of laws, navigation, routes, shipping lanes, fisheries management, and territorial claims, thereby defining the ocean by the human practices but not in terms of the natural laws. Moreover, with the rise of global trade and exploration, the ocean became a highway for commerce and trade, mobilizing the goods, people, and even ideas more freely, enabling the globalization. Steinberg argues that, modern capitalist world-economy relies on imagining the ocean as a space for free movement, undermining the ecological structures and the marine life that are innate within the waters. His argument accelerates the fact of how blue economy is augmenting with new trade policies at the cost of neglecting the issues of damaging eco cultures and losing the sustainability of the planet.

Sublimity which was previously associated with mountains and forests came to be associated with water, because of its immense power, mystery and capacity to evoke awe and wonder

representing the totality that challenges the human understanding of the oceans. The vastness of the oceans embodies a power, both beautiful and terrifying, making humans insignificant and simultaneously igniting the feelings of fear and fascination at their profundity. Serving as a figure of global space, ocean is considered as a realm beyond boundaries of land and nations and with its deep uncharted regions, became the ‘terra incognita’ of the world, thus relocating the mystery once associated with the land to the depths of the sea. Modern novel at sea with its sublimity was born with Robinson Crusoe and reached metaphysical sophistication with *Moby-Dick* by Melville. Men seeking solitude shifted their gaze to the oceans, while the world is being filled with the dystopian societies. Writers and painters have turned their full attention to sea itself as a place of physical and spiritual recreation, in contrast to those historical fictions that dealt with the ships, sailors, their skill in manning them, voyages, with sea just as an afterthought. Steve Menz in his work *An Introduction to the Blue Humanities*, observes Coleridge’s *Rime of the Ancient Mariner* as a linchpin of the Romantic sublime in English poetry. In his words,

“The poem’s stark representations of isolation on a vast sea juxtapose human frailty and inhuman power. From a multiphase blue humanities perspective, the poem depicts multiple encounters with sublime water creatures, including the icebergs of the Southern Ocean, the world-girdling winds of the Roaring Forties and the inhuman encounter with the albatross... Coleridge’s mariner never recognizes himself in his non-human world. Rather, sublime encounter in this ocean remains

opaque, and human agency thoroughly minimized.” (ch.4)

On the other hand, Blue Humanities also comes from a longer tradition of water practices by many communities globally, sharing a genealogical connection to the ocean, whose knowledge helps to understand the ocean’s profound impact on history, culture and identity. Renowned Pacific scholar, a Tongan and Fijian writer, Epeli Hau’ofa, highlights this innate relation of indigenous communities with the ocean in his work, *Our Sea of Islands* (1993) by asserting on the significance of the ocean to the Pacific Islanders. He presents a contrasting view of the ‘Oceania’, his favorite word for Pacific islands, in which people see the islands differently. For outsiders, the view is external, as islands in a far sea, emphasizing the isolation, remoteness, small and masses, dependency and marginality, but for them, as insiders, the view is a sea of islands, a Pacific centered view that sees the ocean not as a barrier but as connective thread, integral to identity, culture, movement and relationships. Epeli, criticizes the Colonial, Western perceptions as the colonial powers brought with them the idea of islands as isolated, hopeless, small places, thus creating the false boundaries. He recalls this idea by stating, “we never thought of ourselves as being from small places. We spent most of our time by the sea where we could see this vast ocean and knew there were other places, beyond, where our friends and relatives were” (xv). Being more than a geographic entity, sea is a home, source of livelihood, identity, memory and history. Hau’ofa urges people to recognize the ocean’s central role and to see the region’s wealth not only in land but in oceanic resources and relationships. Another interesting novel, *The Hungry Tide* by Amitav Ghosh, deals with the sea-threatened Sundarbans, tiny islands in the Bay of Bengal. Nature is shown not as a backdrop but as an active

powerful force. The lives of the people in the area are intimately tied to storms, animals, tides etc. The book depicts the conflict between conservation and environmental rules and the livelihood of the local people. The local communities depend on fishing, forest, produce, etc., but some environmental protection measures threaten their existence. As the protection of environments often comes at the cost of human livelihoods, the novel questions, who benefits from conservation. Amitav Ghosh is not intended to narrate the story of an adventure or romance but he uses the Sundarbans to explore environmental ethics, power, displacement, and how modernity interacts with the tradition of nature. Hence, the novel can be related to the present-day climate crises, addressing the issues of communities living in vulnerable ecologies. Be it Hau'ofa, or Jules Vernes, or Rachel Carson, or Steve Mentz etc., all these writers focus on the reconsideration of the watery planet, nullifying the hegemonic attribution to the land masses and highlights the significance of water as the crux of human life on the planet.

Conclusion:

Blue Humanities gives a hope of imaginative possible features for human intimacy with water. As sea rises glaciers melt as warm air absorbs more moisture, the blue humanities will have much to say and do in our changing ecological condition. Rising sea levels, decline in fresh water availability, threat to marine life as a result of increased Anthropocentric concerns, are the further challenges, that have to be dealt in this frame work. A focus on planetary water through writings and academic scholarships, tend to address the global concerns of today's eco-catastrophic times. Human relationship with water has to be changed. Whether it is hydro criticism of critical oceanic studies or the ocean history or the sub-disciplinary methods ... all together under the banner of

the blue humanities. Human beings shouldn't forget the fact that, conservation, purity and sustainability are the morals of water, which cannot be undermined in the name of anthropocentrism. Following lines from the essay, "The Emergence of Blue Humanities: Traversing Land locked Ecocriticism in the novels of the Floating World", act as a warning to the mankind if the water life is still neglected and leading to the catastrophes,

"The world is creeping toward Darwinism. This 'death by water', will act as a double-edged sword, where, on the one hand, the land will succumb to water, and on the other, the lack of water, the droughts and water crisis will lead to extinction of living beings. This is the wasteland of the modern era manufactures by ongoing Anthropocene activities without consideration for the sustainable management of resources for the future. Thinking beyond the ecocriticism is a key to counter this anthropocentric situation". (44)

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